

Supporting regions to be climate resilient by 2030

NATALIE, a research project, contributes to the objectives of the European Union mission “Adaptation to Climate Change”, whose aim is to empower at least 150 regions and local communities to become climate resilient by 2030.

Unlocking the potential of Nature-based Solutions

NATALIE recognises that different local contexts (climatic, geographical, cultural, legal) require tailored measures such as nature-based solutions (NBS).

Our approach integrates technological, financial and social innovations to ensure the successful implementation of NBS in our 8 cases studies, fostering their social acceptance and monitoring, and assessing their performance.

Our goal is to accelerate the implementation of NBS across Europe by providing evidence of their efficiency and by sharing scientific knowledge to all.

ABOUT NATALIE

43 Partners from 13 countries

Coordinated by OIEau

19.2M€ Sept. 2023 - Aug. 2028

Funded by the European Union

Project funded by

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NATALIE

Accelerating and mainstreaming transformative NATure-bAsed solutions to enhance resiliENCE to climate change for diverse bio-geographical European regions

Demonstrating the efficiency of nature-based solutions as robust measures of adaptation to climate change supporting the European regions to be resilient by 2030

“Nature-based Solutions are solutions inspired and supported by nature, which are cost-effective, simultaneously provide environmental, social and economic benefits and help build resilience.”
European Commission, 2015

Challenges addressed

Climate change poses significant risks to European regions, from extreme floods or forest fires, to slow onset trends like sea level rise and droughts.

NATALIE recognises the barriers to the widespread adoption of NBS, including their integration into initial planning, ensuring continuous monitoring, and overcoming bureaucratic and funding barriers.

To address these challenges, NATALIE is testing, replicating and sharing insights on solutions in 3 key areas: technology and science, financial innovation and societal engagement.

NATALIE's Ambitions

- Implement and monitor NBS across Europe
- Develop digital tools to assess NBS performance under different climate scenarios
- Analyse the cost-benefit of implementing NBS
- Test 3 financial instruments to fund NBS
- Facilitate private investment
- Co-design NBS implementation with local actors
- Engage the whole local communities, through citizen science initiatives
- Gather all the generated knowledge into a friendly digital platform called "NBS Knowledge Booster"

NATALIE CASE STUDIES

18 NBS will be demonstrated at 8 case studies in 6 bio-geographical regions of Europe

1 case study (CS) = 1 demo site (DS) sometimes paired with 1 follower site (FL)
Demo sites implement and assess NBS while follower sites study their replication.

CS#1 - GREECE
Flood & Wildfire risk mitigation

CS#2 - ROMANIA
Fresh water habitat restoration in urban ecosystems

CS#3 - LATVIA & LITHUANIA
Constructed wetlands

CS#4 - SPANISH ARCHIPELAGOS
Alternative water management solutions

CS#5 - BELGIUM
Aquifer recharge for water reuse

CS#6 - FRANCE
Aquatic system restoration & water management

CS#7 - ICELAND
Coastal management with NBS

CS#8 - ITALY
Sustainable river restoration, maintenance & management

12 SITES, 1 SHARED CHALLENGE: CLIMATE CHANGE

